

Comparative Evaluation of Nano-Particles and Magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) Convective Heat and Mass Transfer in a Porous Sheet Medium with Power Index Effects

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ABSTRACT:

The combine study of different nano-particle is a study that tends to evaluate the characteristic behaviour of copper (Cu), Aluminium (Al_2O_3) and Iron (Fe) in terms of heat and mass transfer. These nano-particles plays a significant role in several industries and production processes. relationship. In this study, comparative study of nano-particles and magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) convective heat and mass transfer with power index effects in a porous medium would be considered. the various characteristics of the nano-particles would be analysed to show the preferences in heat/electrical conduction processes. The nanofluid under consideration in this study includes the Copper (Cu), Aluminium (Al_2O_3) and Iron (Fe) with water (H_2O) as the base fluid. The governing equations the flow is transformed using similarity variables and solved numerically using the shooting techniques with Runge-Kutta executed by MATLAB for various values of the controlling parameters of the flow. Graphs and tables were used to depict results. From the study, it is observed that velocity index increase causes a decrease in the fluid velocity of all the nanoparticle, an increase in the temperature of both copper and Alumina and a reduction in the temperature of the Iron, showing a thermal enhancement and decline for copper and Alumina and Iron respectively. Also, the increase in the Magnetic paramater increases the velocity of Copper, Alumina and Iron nanofluid with reduction in the temperature and concentration of the nanofluids.

Keywords: Nano-particles, Buoyancy power index, MHD, Nanofluid, Porous Sheet, heat and mass transfer.

AMS Subject Classification: 76W05, 76X05.

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INTRODUCTION

Metals such as Iron (Fe), Copper (Cu) and Aluminium (Al_2O_3) has been proven beyond reasonable doubt that are very good conductor of heat and electricity. They are characterized by their thermophysical properties (i.e., their ability to conduct heat and transfer electric current). These materials play a vital and significant role in every process of production. Therefore, it is of importance to evaluate these properties to improve more on industrial process. Several Authors over the years has carried out research base on this. Heat and mass transfer across a porous medium of MHD flow of nanofluids with thermal radiation, viscous dissipation, and chemical reaction effect were examined by Shankar and Eshetu [1]. A two-dimensional laminar boundary layer flow of an incompressible cu/alumina water nanofluid across a stretching sheet was studied. The study reveals that an increase in volume fraction results in a decrease in the Cu-water nanofluid's velocity and an increase in Al_2O_3 . Additionally, the fluid's thermal conductivity increases as the volume fraction increases. Kandasamy et al. [2] examined the impact of nanoparticle volume fraction on squeezed MHD water-based Cu, (Al_2O_3) and SWCNTs flow over a porous sensor surface. The study revealed that the presence of heat source/sink, Cu-water plays a significant role in affecting the thermal boundary layer thickness compared to other mixtures in the squeezed flow region.

Damisa and Okedoye [3] investigated the influence of velocity index and the importance of nanofluid flow in magnetohydrodynamics across a stretching porous sheet, incorporating Dufour and ohmic heating effects. A two-dimensional continuous laminar boundary layer over a stretching porous sheet was analyzed. The study indicates that fluid velocity increases with a higher velocity index, whereas velocity, temperature, and mass transfer also rise with an increased volume fraction. Damisa et al. [4] investigated the effects of copper-water nanofluid, along with space and temperature-dependent heat sources and sinks, on magnetohydrodynamic heat and mass transfer in a stretching sheet influenced by buoyancy forces. The study considered a two-dimensional unsteady second-grade nanofluid past a surface driven by a constant pressure gradient and buoyancy. The study reveals that an increment in volume fraction results in heightened motion and temperature, alongside a reduction in mass species of the fluid. Additionally, an increase in buoyancy enhances the velocity, temperature, and concentration of the fluid. Then there is an increment in the velocity and the temperature of the nanofluid.

Convective heat and mass transfer deals with the motion or flow of heat through liquid/gas as a result of the physical motion of the fluid, this means a combine conduction and convective processes which aids in the transfer of energy from one point to another. This is naturally driven by buoyancy force and convective force where external forces are applied. Entropy generation is of great importance and was noticed in industrial and scientific fields including heat transfer in thermal systems which includes mass transfer, heat transfer, and electrical conduction etc. Panya et al [11] in their study of Entropy generation in MHD convective flow with suction or injection for an unsteady flow reveals that the entropy generation and Bejan number erre improved with Hartmann number increase, also larger radiation parameter increases the entropy generation and the Entropy generation due to viscous irreversibility decreases with the increase in Grashof number and Hartmann number. The influence of buoyancy, velocity power index and MHD heat and mass transfer of second-grade nanofluid flow across a stretching-porous sheet with chemical reaction was investigated by Damisa et al [4]. The study revealed that the increasing function of the buoyancy due to temperature and velocity power index leads to the increase in the fluid velocity and temperature. Buoyancy effect on MHD nanofluid flow over a porous medium in the presence of Dufour and Ohmic heating was investigated by Okedoye et al. [5] and found out that an increase in the buoyancy coefficient factor and buoyancy coefficient ratio leads to a decrease in heat and mass transfer and an increase in the skin-friction coefficient.

Power index is a significant parameter in the power-law that describes the behaviour of non-Newtonian fluids. It relates the shear stress to the shear rate and shows if the shear thinness ($n < 1$), shear thickness ($n > 1$) and Newtonian ($n = 1$). Several authors has picked up the interest to examine the relative significant effects of the power-law in flow of fluid. Boxue *et al* [6] examined the effects of flow behaviour index and consistency coefficient on hydrodynamics of power fluids and

particles in fluidized beds. It is shown in the study that the rise in the consistency coefficient causes a rise in the apparent viscosity of fluidizing agent. Abdul *et al* [7], investigated the Radiative nanofluid flow over a slender stretching Riga plate under the impact of exponential heat source/sink. The study is aimed at examining the energy and mass transfer across the mixed convective nanofluid flow over an extending Riga plate. It is revealed in the study that the velocity of the fluid increases with the increase in the thickness parameter and the fluid temperature also increases as the Biot number, Eckert number and heat source factor increases. Anjali Devi and Agneeshwari [8] examined the effect of non-uniform heat and radiation on hydromagnetic dissipative flow with heat and mass fluxes. The study focuses on steady, laminar, two-dimensional hydrodynamic flow of a viscous, incompressible electrically conducting fluid over a nonlinear stretching surface in the presence of non-uniform heat and viscous dissipation. The study revealed that the non-uniform heat parameter and radiation parameter plays a significant role in the control of the thermal boundary layer thickness and temperature. Following Mumtaz *et al.* [9] the power index causes a significant impact in flow of fluids by altering the pattern of the velocity profile, influencing the fluid motion and its gradient, then modifying the flow resistance.

From the mentioned literature above, a combined study of three distinct nanoparticles with water as the nano-based fluid has not been studied. Hence, this study is aimed at evaluating the thermal and electrical conductivity of three Nano-particles (Copper-water, Alumina-water and Iron-water) of Magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) Convective Heat and Mass Transfer Nanofluid flow over a Porous Sheet with the Effects of Power Index.

Mathematical Analysis

A two-dimensional unsteady laminar hybrid nanofluid over a convective heat porous sheet is considered. The fluid is driven by the buoyancy force with the buoyancy power index. The x -axis is the continuous stretching surface and the y -axis is measured normal to the sheet. A magnetic field of strength B_0 is applied in the direction of y -axis. The effect of the modified natural buoyancy model force in Makinde and Animasaun [10] is incorporated into the flow formulation. The nano-particles are copper (Cu), Alumina (Al_2O_3) and Iron (Fe) with water (H_2O) as the base fluid, it is assumed that the base fluid and the nano-particles are in thermal equilibrium and no slip occurs mixture (nanofluid).

The sheet is stretched with a velocity $U_w(x) = ax^m$ and $v_w(x) = S\sqrt{\frac{av(m+1)}{2}}x^{\frac{m-1}{2}}$ is the suction velocity and $S > 0$ is a constant. Also, it is assumed that the temperature and concentration in the walls is T_w and C_w with the ambient temperature and concentration as T_∞ and C_∞ respectively. The thermophysical properties of the nano-particles are as follows: dynamic viscosity (μ_{nf}), density (ρ_{nf}), thermal conductivity (α_{nf}) and the heat capacity (ρC_p) $_{nf}$. Hence, the equation of motion for the two-dimensional equation becomes;

$$\frac{du}{dx} + \frac{dv}{dy} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \frac{\mu_{nf}}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}\right)^2 - \frac{\mu_{nf}}{\rho_{nf} k} u - \frac{\sigma \beta_0^2(x)}{\rho_{nf}} (u - U) + \frac{g \beta_T m + 1}{\rho_{nf} 2} (T - T_\infty) + \frac{g \beta_C m + 1}{\rho_{nf} 2} (C - C_\infty) \quad (2)$$

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \frac{\alpha_{nf}}{(\rho C_p)_{nf}} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} - \frac{1}{(\rho C_p)_{nf}} \frac{\partial q_r}{\partial y} + \frac{\mu_{nf}}{(\rho C_p)_{nf}} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y}\right)^2 + \frac{D_m k_{nf}}{C_s C_p} \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\sigma \beta_0^2}{(\rho C_p)_{nf}} u^2 \quad (3)$$

$$u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} = \frac{D_m k_{nf}}{\tau \rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} + \frac{D_m k_t}{\rho_{nf} C_s C_p} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} - \frac{1}{\rho_{nf}} k_0 (C - C_\infty) \quad (4)$$

Where u and v are the velocity component in the x and y direction respectively. β_T is the volumetric coefficient of thermal expansion of nanofluid, T and C are the temperature and concentration of the nanofluid respectively, q_r is the radiative heat flux, D_m is the mass diffusivity, k_t is the thermal diffusion ratio C_s is the concentration susceptibility, C_p is specific heat at constant pressure, τ is the thermophoretic, k is the permeability of the porous medium, k_0 is the chemical reaction and σ is the electrical conductivity. Shankar and Eshetu[1];

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \rho_{nf} &= (1 - \phi)\rho_f + \phi\rho_s \\ \alpha_{nf} &= \frac{k_{nf}}{(\rho c_p)_{nf}} \\ \mu_{nf} &= \frac{\mu_f}{(1 - \phi)^{2.5}} \\ (\rho c_p)_{nf} &= (\rho c_p)_f \left((1 - \phi) + \phi \frac{(\rho c_p)_s}{(\rho c_p)_f} \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

The thermal conductivity of nanofluid of a spherical Nanoparticle Shankar and Eshetu [1] is given as:

$$k_{nf} = k_f \left[\frac{k_s + 2k_f - 2\phi(k_f - k_s)}{k_s + k_f - \phi(k_f - k_s)} \right] \quad (6)$$

The subscript f and s of the quantities are the base fluid and nanoparticles respectively. According to the Roseland diffusion approximation Hussein [13] and Raptis [12] the radiative heat flux q_r is given by

$$q_r = -\frac{4\sigma^* \partial T^4}{3k^* \partial y} \quad (7)$$

Where σ^* and k^* are the Stefan-Boltzmann constant and the Rosseland mean absorption coefficient respectively. We assumed that the temperature difference within the flow is sufficiently small such that T^4 may be expressed as a linear function of temperature as.

$$T^4 \approx 4T_\infty^3 T - 3T_\infty^4 \quad (8)$$

Substituting Equation (8) into Equation (7) and differentiate with respect to y , we have;

$$\begin{aligned} q_r &= -\frac{4\sigma^* \partial(4T_\infty^3 T - 3T_\infty^4)}{3k^* \partial y} = -\frac{16\sigma^* T_\infty^3 \partial T}{3k^* \partial y} \\ \frac{\partial q_r}{\partial y} &= -\frac{16\sigma^* T_\infty^3 \partial^2 T}{3k^* \partial y^2} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Let } D = \frac{D_m k_{nf}}{c_s c_p} \text{ and } D_1 = \frac{D_m k_t}{\rho_{nf} c_s c_p} \quad (10)$$

Substituting equation (9), (10) into (3) and (4), we have equation (1) to (4) as;

$$\frac{du}{dx} + \frac{dv}{dy} = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \frac{\mu_{nf}}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 - \frac{\mu_{nf}}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{1}{k} u - \frac{\sigma \beta_0^2(x)}{\rho_{nf}} (u - U) + \frac{g \beta_T m + 1}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{m + 1}{2} (T - T_\infty) + \frac{g \beta_C m + 1}{\rho_{nf}} \frac{m + 1}{2} (C - C_\infty) \quad (12)$$

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \frac{\alpha_{nf}}{(\rho c_p)_{nf}} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} - \frac{16 \sigma^* T_\infty^3}{3 k^* (\rho c_p)_{nf}} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\mu_{nf}}{(\rho c_p)_{nf}} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2 + D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\sigma \beta_0^2}{(\rho c_p)_{nf}} u^2 \quad (13)$$

$$u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} = D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} + D_1 \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} - \frac{1}{\rho_{nf}} k_0 (C - C_\infty) \quad (14)$$

with the boundary conditions;

$$u = U_w(x), v = -v_w(x), -k_f \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = h_f (T_s - T_f), C = h_f (C_s - C_f) \text{ at } y = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$u \rightarrow 0, T \rightarrow T_\infty, C \rightarrow C_\infty \text{ as } y \rightarrow \infty$$

Similarity Transformation

The governing equations of the flow is transformed into ordinary differential equation (ODE) by applying the stream function and similarity variable defined by Anjali and Agneeshwari [8]

$$\psi(x, y) = \sqrt{\frac{2av}{m+1}} x^{m+1} f(\eta), \quad \eta(x, y) = y \sqrt{\frac{a(m+1)}{2v}} x^{\frac{m-1}{2}} \quad (16)$$

$$T = T_\infty + (T_w - T_\infty) x^{2m} \sqrt{\frac{2v}{a(m+1)}} \theta(\eta), \quad C = C_\infty + (C_w - C_\infty) x^{2m} \sqrt{\frac{2v}{a(m+1)}} \varphi(\eta)$$

The stream function ψ satisfies the continuity equation (1). The velocity component $f'(\eta)$, dimensionless temperature $\theta(\eta)$ and the dimensionless concentration $\varphi(\eta)$ are given by;

$$u = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} = ax^m f(\eta), \quad v = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} = -\sqrt{\frac{av(m+1)}{2}} x^{\frac{m-1}{2}} f(\eta) - \sqrt{\frac{av(m+1)}{2}} x^{\frac{m-1}{2}} \frac{m-1}{m+1} \eta f'(\eta)$$

$$\theta(\eta) = \frac{T-T_\infty}{(T_w-T_\infty)}, \quad \varphi(\eta) = \frac{C-C_\infty}{(C_w-C_\infty)} \quad (17)$$

Employing the similarity variables and the stream functions (16) and (17), the partial differential equation (PDE) (2), (3) and (4) with the boundary conditions (15) governing the fluid flow is transformed into the nonlinear ordinary differential equation (ODE) as;

$$f''' + \phi_1 \left(f''^2 + ff'' + \frac{m-1}{m+1} f'f'' - \frac{M}{\phi_2} (f' - 1) + Gr_t \theta + Gr_c \varphi \right) - \frac{2m}{m+1} f'^2 - \frac{1}{k} f' = 0 \quad (18)$$

$$\left(1 + \frac{4R}{3} \right) \theta'' + Pr \phi_4 \frac{k_f}{k_{nf}} \left(\frac{m-1}{m+1} f'\theta' - \frac{m-1}{2} f\theta' + f\theta' - \frac{4}{m+1} f\theta + \frac{MEc}{\phi_4} f'^2 - Du\varphi'' \right) = 0 \quad (19)$$

$$\varphi'' + \frac{1}{Sc} \left(\frac{m-1}{m+1} f'\varphi' - f\varphi' - \frac{4m}{m+1} f'\varphi + \gamma\varphi \right) + Sr\theta'' = 0 \quad (20)$$

The corresponding boundary conditions are;

$$f(0) = S, f'(0) = 1, \theta'(0) = Bi(1 - \theta), \varphi'(0) = 1 \quad \text{at } \eta = 0$$

$$f'(\infty) \rightarrow 0, \theta(\infty) \rightarrow 0, \varphi(\infty) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } \eta \rightarrow \infty \quad (21)$$

Where $\phi_1 = (1 - \phi)^{2.5} \left(1 - \phi + \phi \left(\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_f} \right) \right)$, $\phi_2 = \left(1 - \phi + \phi \left(\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_f} \right) \right)$, $M = \frac{\sigma \beta_0^2(x)}{\left(1 - \phi + \phi \left(\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_f} \right) \right)}$,

$Gr_t = \frac{g\beta_T(T_w-T_\infty)x^{\frac{m}{2}}}{av}$, $Gr_c = \frac{g\beta_T(C_w-C_\infty)x^{\frac{m}{2}}}{av}$, $R = \frac{4\sigma^*T_\infty^3}{3k^*k_{nf}}$ is the thermal radiation parameter, $Pr = \frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f}$ is the Prandtl number, $\phi_3 = (1 - \phi)(\rho C_p)_f + \phi(\rho C_p)_s$, $\phi_4 = \left(1 - \phi + \phi \left(\frac{(\rho C_p)_s}{(\rho C_p)_f} \right) \right)$, $Ec = \frac{a^2 x^{2m}}{\nu_f(C_p)_f(T_w-T_\infty)}$ is the Eckert number, $M = \frac{\sigma \beta_0^2(x)}{\alpha \rho_f}$ is the magnetic parameter and $Du = \frac{aD(C_w-C_\infty)}{\nu_f(T_w-T_\infty)}$ is the Dufour number, $Sc = \frac{\nu_f}{D}$ is the Schmidt number, $\gamma = \frac{D_1 k_0}{D^2 a(m+1)}$ is the chemical reaction parameter and $Sr = \frac{D_1(T_w-T_\infty)}{D(C_w-C_\infty)} \frac{a(m+1)}{2\nu}$ is the Soret number.

Rate of Flow at the wall: The Engineering parameters of interest on the flow are skin friction coefficient C_f and Nusselt number Nu_x and local Sherwood number Sh_x defined respectively as;

$$C_f = \frac{2\tau_w}{\rho_f u_w(x)}, Nu_x = \frac{xq_w}{k_f(T_w-T_\infty)}, Sh_x = \frac{xJ_w}{D(C_w-C_\infty)} \quad (22)$$

Where the wall shear stress τ_w , the surface heat flux Nu_x and the mass flux J_w at the surface is given by;

$$\tau_w = \mu_{nf} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0}, q_w = - \left(k_{nf} + \frac{16\sigma^* T_\infty^3}{3k^*} \right) \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0}, J_w = -D \left(\frac{\partial c}{\partial y} \right)_{y=0} \quad (23)$$

Substituting equation (22) into equation (23), the skin friction coefficient C_f and Nusselt number Nu_x and local Sherwood number Sh_x becomes;

$$\sqrt{Re_x} C_f = \frac{\sqrt{2(m+1)} f''(0)}{(1-\phi)^{2.5}}, \frac{Nu_x}{\sqrt{Re_x}} = k_T \sqrt{\frac{m+1}{2}} \left(1 + \frac{4R}{3} \right) \theta'(0), \frac{Sh_x}{\sqrt{Re_x}} = \sqrt{\frac{m+1}{2}} \varphi'(0) \quad (24)$$

Where $Re_x = \frac{u_w x}{\nu}$ is the local Reynold number.

Table 1. The Thermophysical Properties of Water, Copper, Alumina and Iron

PHYSICAL QUANTITIES	NANOPARTICLES PROPERTIES		
	Density ρ (Kg/m ²)	Specific heat capacity C_p (J/Kgk)	Thermal conductivity K(W/mk)
Pure Water (H ₂ O)	997.1	4179	0.613
Copper (Cu)	8933	385	400
Alumina (Al ₂ O ₃)	3970	765	40
Iron (Fe)	7800	450	79.5

Numerical solution

The ordinary differential equation (18), (19) and (20) with the boundary condition (21) is solved using the bvp4c (boundary value problem of fourth-order) finite-difference approach built in code available in MATLAB subroutines

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2. Nano-Particles Volume Fraction Effect on the Flow Field when $m = 1.0, M = 0.3, G_t = 0.2, G_c = 1.0, k = 1.0, Pr = 3.0, R = 0.4, Ec = 0.1, Du = 0.2$ and $Sc = 0.2$

Parameter (Volume fraction (ϕ))	C_f			Nu			Sh		
	Cu-water	Al-water	Fe-water	Cu-water	Al-water	Fe-water	Cu-water	Al-water	Fe-water
0.0	1.3745	1.2171	1.2733	1.5661	1.3882	1.4458	1.7486	1.4456	1.5008
0.3	1.3689	1.2676	1.1571	1.5462	1.4340	1.2978	1.7400	1.4638	1.3469
0.6	1.3684	1.2733	1.2722	1.5946	1.4458	1.4591	1.7024	1.5008	1.5102

Table 3. Velocity Index (m), Magnetic Parameter (M), Buoyancy Ratio due to Temperature (Grt), Buoyancy Ratio due to Concentration (Grc), Radiative Parameter (R) and Dufour Parameter (Du) with Wall Rate Transfer when the Volume Fraction $\phi = 0.2$

Parameter (m, M, Grt, Grc, R and Du when $\phi = 0.2$)	C_f			Nu			Sh		
	Cu-water	Al-water	Fe-water	Cu-water	Al-water	Fe-water	Cu-water	Al-water	Fe-water
m									
0.8	1.4854	1.1993	1.3589	1.6272	1.2696	1.4738	1.7617	1.3246	1.5131

0.9	1.4786	1.2898	1.3568	1.6202	1.3853	1.4413	1.7605	1.4354	1.5195
1.0	1.3036	1.3434	1.3553	1.4248	1.3958	1.4591	1.5129	1.4307	1.5102
M									
5.0	1.5992	1.2996	1.4118	1.9298	1.5605	1.6757	2.2850	1.8169	1.9998
5.5	1.3448	1.2997	1.4153	1.5242	1.5605	1.7087	1.6834	1.8169	1.9568
6.0	1.6119	1.3012	1.4187	1.9151	1.5679	1.7216	2.3231	1.8344	2.0389
Grt									
0.2	1.5992	1.2346	1.4118	1.9298	1.4095	1.6757	2.2850	1.6793	1.9998
0.4	1.6101	1.2992	1.4157	1.8339	1.5559	1.6832	2.0364	1.8025	1.9212
0.6	1.6742	1.3005	1.4196	2.0771	1.5593	1.6907	2.4466	1.8068	2.0152
Grc									
1.0	1.6609	1.2954	1.3282	1.7919	1.4184	1.4423	1.8643	1.4428	1.4945
1.5	1.5290	1.2169	1.5188	1.6408	1.3012	1.6157	1.6962	1.3435	1.6410
2.0	1.5407	1.2928	1.5016	1.6821	1.3778	1.6006	1.7279	1.4016	1.6301
R									
1.0	1.7000	1.2833	1.3009	1.9355	1.3718	1.2777	2.0247	1.4342	1.2009
2.0	1.7371	1.3818	1.3282	2.0996	1.5025	1.4423	2.2785	1.5621	1.4945
2.5	1.7608	1.3152	1.5374	2.0908	1.4224	1.6683	2.2484	1.4835	1.6971
k									
1.0	1.6609	1.3818	1.3255	1.7919	1.5025	1.4408	1.8643	1.5621	1.4975
1.5	1.5714	1.3176	1.2734	1.7204	1.4264	1.3430	1.7889	1.4884	1.3842
2.0	1.5341	1.4923	1.3282	1.6859	1.5530	1.4423	1.7424	1.5834	1.4945

This study compares the thermal and electrical conductivity using the thermophysical properties of copper (Cu), Alumina (Al_2O_3) and Iron (Fe) with water as base fluid. Fig. 1, 2 and 3 shows the effects of nanofluid volume fraction (ϕ) on the fluid velocity, temperature and concentration respectively. It is observed from Fig.1 that the increment in the volume fraction (ϕ) of the nanofluids experiences a decline in the profiles of the nanofluids velocity and on the other hand, from Fig. 2 and 3, an increase in the nanofluids temperature and concentration is experienced respectively. Fig.4, 5 and 6 indicates Effect of velocity index (m) on fluid Velocity, temperature and concentration. From Fig.4, it is observed that the increasing value of the velocity index (m) causes a decrease in the fluid velocity. From Fig.5, it is observed that there is an increase in the temperature profile of both copper (Cu) and Alumina (Al_2O_3) and a decrease in the temperature profile of the Iron (Fe) when the velocity index (m) is present, showing a thermal enhancement and decline for copper (Cu) and Alumina (Al_2O_3) and Iron (Fe) respectively. From Fig.6 it is observed that an increment in the velocity index (m) leads to a reduction in the fluid concentration of all the nanofluid particles. Fig.7, 8 and 9 depicts the disturbance of the magnetic parameter (M) by fluid velocity, temperature and concentration. It is observed from the various figures and profiles of both Copper (Cu), Alumina (Al_2O_3) and the Iron (Fe) that there is an upshoot in the velocity and a down shoot in the fluid temperature and concentration respectively, while there exist an increasing function of the magnetic parameter (M). Fig.10 and 11 shows the effects of Buoyancy due to concentration on the fluid velocity and concentration respectively. From both figures, it is observed that the increase in the buoyancy due to concentration parameter (Gr_c) brings about the increase in the fluid velocity and a decrease in the fluid concentration. Fig.12 and 13 indicates the effects of buoyancy due to temperature on the fluid concentration and velocity. It is seen from the figures that the increasing effect of the parameter leads to the decreasing effect of the fluid concentration and an increasing effect of the fluid velocity. Fig.14, 15 and 16 depict the effect of the porous medium parameter (k) on the fluid velocity, temperature and concentration. From the figures, it is shown that the increase in the porous medium parameter leads to an increase in the motion of the fluid and a decrease in the fluid temperature and concentration respectively. Fig.17, 18 and 19 shows the effect of thermal radiation parameter (R) on fluid velocity, temperature and concentration. From the figures, the fluid velocity and temperature of all the nanofluid particles increase and the concentration decreases when there is an increase in the thermal radiation parameter. Fig.20, 21 and 22 depict the effect of Prandtl number (Pr) on the fluid velocity, temperature and concentration. The increase in the prandtl number brings about the decrease in the velocity, temperature and concentration of the nanofluids at every point.

Table 2.1 shows the behaviour of volume fraction (ϕ) on the flow field, skin friction coefficient $f''(0)$, Nusselt number $\theta'(0)$ and the Sherwood number $\phi'(0)$ at volume fraction $\phi = 0.0, 0.3$ and 0.6 when $m = 1.0, M = 0.3, Gr_t = 0.2, Gr_c = 1.0, k = 1.0, Pr = 3.0, R = 0.4, Ec = 0.1, Du = 0.2$ and $Sc = 0.2$.

It is observed from the table that an increase in the volume fraction causes a sinusoidal effect on the skin friction coefficient $C_{u-water}$ and $C_{Fe-water}$ with a strict decreasing effect on the $C_{Al-water}$. Also, the Nusselt number for the $Cu-water$, $Fe-water$ and $Al-water$. Also exhibit similar effect as that of the skin-friction coefficient. While there is a reduction in the $Cu-water$ and $Al-water$ a sinusoidal effect for the $Fe-water$ of the Sherwood number.

Table 2.2 show the depicts the various effects of parameters on the flow field when the volume fraction $\phi = 0.2$. It is observed from the table that the increasing function of the value of the velocity index parameter (m) causes an increase in the skin-friction coefficient of $Cu-water$, $Al-water$ and $Fe-water$. The Nusselt number of $Cu-water$ and $Fe-water$ show a decrease and increase when the values of the velocity index was amplify, while the $Al-water$ grow. The Sherwood number shows a decreasing effect for the $Cu-water$, a sinusoidal effect for $Al-water$ and $Fe-water$. The rise in the Magnetic parameter (M) brings about the sinusoidal effect of the skin-friction coefficient for $Cu-water$ and an amplifying effect of the skin-friction coefficient for $Al-water$ and $Fe-water$. Sinusoidal effect of Nusselt number for $Cu-water$, $Al-water$ and $Fe-water$. Then the Sherwood number exhibits a sinusoidal effect for both $Cu-water$ and $Al-water$ and an increase for $Fe-water$. With the increase in the Buoyancy due to temperature. It is observed that the skin-friction coefficient shows a sinusoidal effect for $cu-water$ and $Al-water$ and an increase in the $Fe-water$. Also, there is a sinusoidal effect on the Nusselt number for the $cu-water$ and an increase in $Al-water$ and $Fe-water$ flow field, then a sinusoidal effect on the Sherwood for $Cu-water$ and $Fe-water$ with an increasing function for the $Al-water$.

The increase in the Buoyancy due to concentration parameter (Gr_c), the skin-friction coefficient for $cu-water$ and $Al-water$ exhibits a sinusoidal effect and a decrease for the $Fe-water$ flow field. The Nusselt number exhibits sinusoidal effect for both $cu-water$, $Al-water$ and $Fe-water$ flow field which is also similar for the Sherwood flow field. The increasing function of the radiation parameter (R) results in increase in the skin-friction coefficient for the $Cu-water$ and $Fe-water$, while there is a sinusoidal effect for the $Al-water$ flow field. The Nusselt number increases for both $Cu-water$ and $Fe-water$, while the $Al-water$ exhibits a sinusoidal effect in the flow field. Then, the Sherwood exhibits a sinusoidal effect for $Cu-water$ and $Al-water$ and an increase for the $Fe-water$. With the increasing function of the porous medium parameter (k), the skin-friction exhibit a sinusoidal effect for $Al-water$ and $Fe-water$, while a decrease is experienced for the $Cu-water$, while there is a sinusoidal effect for both $cu-water$, $Al-water$ and $Fe-water$ and share a similar sinusoidal of the Sherwood for $Cu-water$, $Al-water$ and $Fe-water$.

Figure 1. Behaviour of volume fraction (ϕ) on Velocity of fluid

Figure 2. Behaviour of volume fraction (ϕ) on fluid Temperature

Figure 3. Effect of volume fraction (ϕ) on fluid Concentration

Figure 4. Effect of velocity index (m) on fluid Velocity

Figure 5. Nature of velocity index (m) on fluid Temperature

Figure 6. Nature of velocity index (m) on fluid Concentration

Figure 7. Magnetic parameter (M) effect on fluid Velocity

Figure 8. Magnetic parameter (M) effect on fluid Temperature

Figure 9. Interaction of Magnetic parameter (M) on fluid Concentration

Figure 10. Interaction of Buoyancy Ratio (Gr_c) on fluid Velocity

Figure 11. Buoyancy Ratio (Gr_c) nature on Concentration of fluid

Figure 12. Buoyancy (Gr_t) nature on Concentration of fluid

Figure 13. Effect of Buoyancy (Gr_t) on fluid Velocity

Figure 14. Effect of Porous medium parameter (k) on fluid Velocity

Figure 15. Behaviour of Porous medium parameter (k) on fluid Temperature

Figure 16. Behaviour of Porous medium parameter (k) on fluid Concentration

Figure 17. Interaction of Thermal Radiation parameter (R) on fluid Velocity

Figure 18. Interaction of Thermal Radiation parameter (R) on fluid Temperature

Figure 19. Thermal Radiation parameter (R) effect on fluid Concentration

Figure 20. Prandtl Number (Pr) effect on fluid Velocity

Figure 21. Prandtl Number (Pr) nature on fluid Temperature

Figure 22. Prandtl Number (Pr) nature on fluid Concentration

CONCLUSION

The presence of the magnetic parameter does not always bring about the decrease in the fluid velocity. However, the presence of the magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) generally leads to the decrease of fluid velocity due to its Lorentz force serving as a dragging force that tends to oppose the direction of fluid motion. This is peculiar to several MHD flow.

It is clearly shown that it is not in all cases the magnetic parameter leads to the rise in the temperature of the viscous fluid. The increase in the temperature of the fluid is often as a result of viscous dissipation and the Lorentz force, on the other hand, there are some specific cases or some fluid properties where the temperature of the fluid decreases or shows no significant increase or decrease. Hence, the following conclusions;

1. The rise in the volume fraction of the nanofluids lead to a decline of the nanofluids velocity of the Copper-water, Alumina-water and Iron-water nanofluid, then increase in the nanofluids temperature and concentration is experienced.
2. The rising values of the velocity index results in the reduction of the fluid velocity for Copper-water, Alumina-water and the Iron-water nanofluid. with increase in the temperature of both copper-water and Alumina-water and a decrease in the temperature of the Iron-water, this shows a thermal enhancement and decline for copper and Alumina and Iron and a decrease in the fluid concentration of all the nanofluid particles.
3. Both Copper-water, Alumina-water and the Iron-water velocity increases, fluid temperature and concentration decreases respectively with the increasing function of the magnetic parameter.
4. The enlargement in the buoyancy due to concentration parameter brings about the reduction in the Copper-water, Alumina-water and Iron-water nanofluid velocity and a decrease in the nanofluids concentration. The increasing effect of the buoyancy due to temperature leads to the decreasing effect of the nanofluids concentration and an increasing effect for all the nanofluid velocity.
5. The increase in the porous medium parameter leads to an increase in the motion of the nanofluids and a decrease in the nanofluids temperature and concentration.
6. The fluid velocity and temperature of both Copper-water, Alumina-water and Iron-water nanofluid increases and the concentration of the nanofluids decreases when there is an increase in the thermal radiation parameter. The increase in the prandtl number brings about the decrease in the velocity, temperature and concentration of the nanofluids.
7. In summary, Copper ranks first in heat transfer and electrical current transfer, Aluminum ranks second, and Iron tanks third. For heat absorption and retention, Iron generally exhibits greater heat storage capacity, followed by Copper and Aluminum. Therefore, the choice of material depends

on whether the application requires rapid heat/electrical conduction(Copper and Aluminum) or greater heat retention (Iron).

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